

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OVERVIEW OF ACCESS TO FINANCING FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND SOLAR ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES FOR SMES IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in the sustainable development of the economy. The implementation of energy efficiency and solar energy technologies not only reduces operational costs but also contributes to environmental and economic sustainability. Access to financing for integrating these technologies presents several challenges. This research aims to examine the current state of financing for energy efficiency and solar energy technology implementation for SMEs in Georgia and to develop recommendations for stimulating mechanisms in this direction. To achieve the study's objectives, a mixed-methods approach was adopted. The qualitative research included desk research on foreign and Georgian publications, as well as legislative and policy documents related to energy efficiency and solar energy investments. The quantitative research involved structured interviews with top management of Georgian banks and field professionals. Additionally, a survey was conducted among government organizations, industry associations, and companies utilizing solar power plants. This also included in-depth group interviews with solar power system installers to identify challenges in implementing these technologies for SMEs.

The research analyzed the barriers and opportunities for SME financing, developed recommendations for necessary reforms to support relevant government agencies, and aimed to enhance the activities of international financial and specialized organizations, as well as commercial banks, in promoting investments and financing in energy efficiency and solar energy projects for SMEs.

Keywords: SMEs, Energy Efficiency, Solar Energy, Financing, IFIs, Georgian Banks, Green Loans, Renewable Energy.

Relevance of the Topic

In Georgia, as well as globally, SMEs play a significant role in the sustainable development of the economy (Tsutskiridze et al., 2024; Tsutskiridze, Charaia, 2023). They account for 67% of employment and approximately 62% of the total value added, making their impact on the environment substantial. SMEs are considered the backbone of the economy, and their development is important for any country in two ways: firstly, in terms of increasing national welfare, which includes reducing social and financial inequality, and secondly, in terms of reducing environmental impact. While the effect of individual enterprises is small, their total number surpasses that of large enterprises. Reducing energy intensity in SMEs will have a significant impact on the country's economic and ecological efficiency. The 2021-2025 Strategy for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises in Georgia has identified improving access to finance as a priority, with the seventh priority being the promotion of green economy development.

Significant funds have been allocated at the national level to implement sustainable development and climate change measures in Georgia, directed both towards green financing (energy efficiency, renewable energy sources) and towards creating a market for green goods and services (specifically, energy-efficient construction products). Green technologies

are characterized by high costs and 90% are imported from abroad. According to the World Bank's 2019 Enterprise Survey, access to finance is cited as the second-largest obstacle after instability. This is confirmed by data from the National Bank of Georgia's Credit Conditions Survey (NBG. Credit Conditions Survey, p.7, 2024).

According to the data available to the National Bank, the interest rates on national currency loans did not change (Anguridze et al., 2015), and amounted to 13.2% for SME loans. For SME loans issued in euros, the interest rate declined by 0.3 percentage points to 7.0%. For USD-denominated loans, the interest rate slightly decreased to 8.4%. In the first quarter of 2024, the share of rejected loans did not change significantly. Compared to the previous quarter, the share of rejected loans in SME loans issued in national currency remained at 20%, while for foreign currency SME loans, the share of rejected loans declined to 9% (NBG. Credit Conditions Survey, p.8, 2024).

The data presented by NBG allows us to conclude that the interest rates on SME loans have been higher compared to those for large enterprises since May 2021, though they have matched the rates for large companies by the third quarter of 2023. This is a positive trend but remains a hindrance from the perspective of SME development. Regarding rejected

applications for SMEs, the number is relatively high and increasing.

When analyzing the structure of investment costs for SMEs, 70% is covered by internal resources, with bank credit coming in second. The situation has not significantly improved since 2013 when the share of SME funds was 73%-75%. High collateral requirements are a major obstacle in the crediting process, with collateral requirements amounting to 191% for SMEs and 195% for medium-sized enterprises (Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia, 2021).

Thus, SMEs play a decisive role in the sustainable development of the economy (Sikharulidze, Charaia, 2018; Lashkhi et al., 2022a; 2022b). The process of implementing energy efficiency and solar energy technologies not only reduces operational costs but also promotes environmental and economic sustainability. It is undeniable that access to financing for integrating these technologies is fraught with difficulties.

All of the above defines the relevance of the issue, with the aim of the research being to examine the current state of financing for energy efficiency and solar energy technologies for SMEs in Georgia, identify barriers, and develop recommendations for stimulating mechanisms in this area.

Research Design

Based on the research aim, the following objectives are set:

- Examine barriers and opportunities for SME financing at various developmental levels, both globally and in Georgia.
- Identify necessary reforms to support government structures and determine the role of international organizations in promoting investments and financing for energy efficiency and solar energy projects for SMEs.
- Analyze the activities undertaken by Georgian financial institutions in this regard.

The target groups of the research include:

- Various financial institutions (international organizations, international financial institutions, Georgian banks).
- Representatives of companies that have utilized credit, as well as representatives from companies, associations, and government institutions involved in the process.
- Government agencies.

The research methods employed to achieve the goals and objectives of the study include both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative methods comprised in-depth interviews and desk research, which involved analyzing existing foreign and Georgian publications and legislative-policy documents related to investments and financing in energy efficiency and solar energy projects.

Quantitative methods were used to identify problematic issues related to the implementation of energy-efficient and solar energy technologies for SMEs. A structured interview was conducted with professionals in the field, and a survey was carried out involving sector-specific entities, including

government organizations, associations, companies engaged in the installation of solar power systems, and companies that use solar power plants.

Literature Review

Access to financing for integrating energy-efficient technologies is characterized by challenges. Therefore, it is important to discuss the main barriers and opportunities faced by SMEs in financing these technologies in different countries. This literature review aims to examine contemporary financial mechanisms tailored to SMEs for adopting sustainable energy solutions.

The review of literature related to the research topic highlights the barriers encountered by SMEs when accessing financing for energy-efficient and solar energy technologies:

High Investment Costs and Collateral Requirements: These technologies generally require substantial upfront capital investments (Smith et al., 2022), which financial institutions often require significant collateral to secure, posing an insurmountable barrier for many SMEs (Sheikh et al., 2019), despite their long-term savings (Gupta & Barua, 2018).

Information Asymmetry and Lack of Technical Expertise: The limited availability of information about financing options and the benefits of energy-efficient and solar energy technologies can be a significant impediment to decision-making (Jones & Lee, 2018; Bullier & Milin, 2013).

Perceived Risk: Lenders may perceive SMEs as higher-risk businesses, leading to stricter credit criteria and higher interest rates for renewable energy projects (Gupta & Barua, 2018; Wislade, Michie, & Vernon, 2017).

Complex Application Procedures: The loan application process is often lengthy and labor-intensive, which hinders financing (Dupont & Oberthür, 2015). Recent studies also confirm this challenge and emphasize the need to address the issue.

Political and Regulatory Uncertainty: Inconsistent policies, ambiguous regulations, and unstable market conditions create uncertainty that hinders financial institutions from investing in renewable energy projects for SMEs (Brown & Morrad, 2020). Stable policy frameworks and clear regulatory guidelines are essential for encouraging private sector investments in sustainable energy projects, especially under the challenging circumstances, such as a Coronomic crisis (Papava, Charaia, 2020; 2021; 2022), governmental debt management challenges (Charaia, Papava, 2021; Charaia, Lashkhi 2022) and etc.

Despite the challenges in financing, potential sources for financing SME energy-efficient and solar energy projects include:

Traditional Bank Loans: This type of loan is currently one of the main sources of financing, although qualification criteria have been (Deloitte, 2016) and remain strict (World Bank, 2023).

Specialized Loan Products: Financial institutions increasingly offer loans tailored to energy-efficient and solar energy technologies for SMEs, often providing flexible terms and lower interest rates

to encourage investments in sustainable energy solutions. Innovative financial instruments, such as green bonds (EU, 2023; Azhgaliyeva & Kapsalyamova, 2023), can mobilize private capital for renewable energy projects for SMEs (World Bank, 2023).

Government grants and initiatives are crucial resources for financing SMEs:

Government funding through grants, tax incentives, and rebates is essential for supporting SME financing and may vary by region and program (DSIRE, 2024; IRENA, 2023). It can be asserted that targeted government incentives play a crucial role in overcoming financial barriers and stimulating SME investments in renewable energy projects (Wang & Zheng, 2018). Local governments and corporations also issue "green bonds," considering various tax exemptions (IMF, 2022).

Contemporary Financing Options for SMEs include:

- **Crowdfunding and Alternative Lending:** Online platforms play a significant role in alternative financing for SMEs, often with more lenient qualification requirements compared to traditional banks (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022).

- **P2P Lending Platforms:** These platforms, focusing on sustainability, connect investors directly with borrowers (European Commission, 2024).

- **Community Development Financial Institutions (CDFIs):** CDFIs serve underprivileged community members, offering loans tailored to specific needs (CDFIs, 2024; Procredit Bank, 2022).

Additional Modern Options for Financing Energy-Efficient and Solar Energy Technologies:

- **Energy Performance Contracting (EPC):** This is an agreement between an SME and an Energy Service Company (ESCO) to finance and implement energy-efficient and solar technologies based on shared cost savings and guaranteed energy reductions (EU, 2020). For example, the Guaranteed Savings Model (EPC GS) involves ESCO assuming technical risks while the client secures a bank loan. This model is popular in countries such as the Czech Republic, Denmark, Canada, and Thailand (IEA, 2018).

- **Solar Power Purchase Agreements (PPA):** SMEs can enter into solar power purchase agreements to avoid upfront costs by purchasing solar electricity through a long-term contract (Solar Energy Industry Association, 2018).

- **Green Leasing:** Lessors offer reduced lease payments or cover installation costs for energy-efficient technologies (US Green Building Council, 2024), providing an additional modern financing option for SMEs.

Thus, the literature review on the topic suggests that to improve access to financing for energy-efficient and solar energy technology projects for SMEs, it is advisable to:

- **Develop targeted financial products:** Tailor loan products and risk assessment criteria to SME-specific needs and risk types.

- **Simplify the application process:** Streamline application procedures and provide technical assistance to SMEs.

- **Raise awareness and build capacity:** Educate SMEs about available financing options.

- **Promote innovative financing models:** Encourage the use of crowdfunding, green bonds, and other innovative financial instruments.

- **Foster public-private partnerships:** Collaboration between governments, financial institutions, and other stakeholders can create broader and more effective support for SME financing in energy-efficient and solar energy projects.

Analysis of SME Financing for Energy-Efficient and Solar Technologies in Georgia - current financing landscape. To evaluate SME involvement in energy-efficient and solar technologies in Georgia, we need to assess investments from various financial sources:

International Financial Institutions (IFIs): Organizations such as the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), European Investment Bank (EIB), German KfW, and Austrian Development Bank (ADB) have established credit lines dedicated to environmental protection. These credit lines are utilized by local Georgian banks to fund energy-efficient and solar projects. The Green Growth Fund (GGF) and Global Climate Partnership Fund (GCPF) also play significant roles in this sector, with the Green Climate Fund (GCF) supporting EBRD's sustainable loans.

OECD and EU Projects: The OECD provides long-term financing through Georgian banks, while the EU4Environment project, funded by multiple international bodies, allocated approximately 20 million euros to support environmental projects from 2019 to 2022.

EBRD's Energy Credit Program: Supported by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Finance and GCF, the EBRD's Energy Credit program invested 54 million dollars in housing and SME projects, distributing over 42 million euros through commercial banks such as TBC Bank and Bank of Georgia.

Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF): This facility provides loans between €300,000 and €1.5 million through banks like ProCredit Bank and TBC Bank. The EBRD remains a major investor, allocating 1.703 billion euros to green projects in Georgia between 2016 and 2021.

EIB and KfW Contributions: The EIB has committed 165 million euros for SMEs through Georgian banks and provides guarantees under the "EU Financing for Innovators" scheme. KfW supported hydropower projects with a 25 million euro loan. The Global Climate Partnership Fund focuses on green economy development, benefiting SMEs.

Green Loan Trends. In 2022, green loans in Georgia totaled 486 million lari (\$180 million), marking a 16% increase from 2021. By the end of 2022, green loans constituted 3.2% of the total loan portfolio, up from 2.2% in 2020. TBC Bank led the market with a 45% share. However, high transaction

costs and a limited customer base restrict the growth of green loans.

Challenges and Government Initiatives. Georgia has committed to renewable energy through various agreements and introduced incentives like Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs), tax incentives, and low-interest loans. Despite these efforts, challenges remain, including regulatory gaps, limited financial resources, capacity-building needs, and market barriers.

To meet the research objectives, structured interviews were conducted with top managers from three major Georgian banks: JSC Bank of Georgia, JSC TBC Bank, and JSC ProCredit Bank. These banks are recognized leaders in financing energy-efficient and solar energy technologies.

Loan Financing Overview:

✓ **Bank of Georgia** financed 20 SMEs for solar energy projects by December 31, 2023, but did not provide loans for energy-efficient technologies.

✓ **TBC Bank** financed up to 10 SMEs for solar panel purchases, with 0.5 MW solar stations in operation and 1 MW stations expected in 2024.

✓ **ProCredit Bank** financed 50 SMEs for solar energy, issuing over 2,000 loans for energy efficiency since 2012.

Loan Conditions:

✓ **Bank of Georgia:** Loan conditions were standard, based on business needs, without specified details.

✓ **TBC Bank:** Operates on a "project finance" principle, covering 70% of project value with up to 18-year terms, requiring collateral.

✓ **ProCredit Bank:** Offers competitive rates, with terms dependent on factors like company strength, potentially offering 0% collateral for financially strong companies.

Loan Rejection Criteria: Common reasons across all banks: Insufficient collateral, inadequate credit history, difficulty in risk forecasting, poor business plans, and high risk.

Financing Sources: Bank of Georgia and TBC Bank use both bank resources and international credit lines. **ProCredit Bank** also utilizes these resources, with 90% of its portfolio consisting of SME loans.

Government Support and Alternative Financing: Bank of Georgia and TBC Bank highlighted government programs like "Produce Georgia" and subsidy initiatives. **ProCredit Bank** mentioned the importance of government support through interest rate subsidies and guarantee schemes.

Alternative Financing: ProCredit Bank offers leasing but does not currently offer other alternative financing options, such as P2P or B2B platforms.

Financial Education: All banks recognize that a low level of financial education in the high-tech sector impedes SME access to financing, stressing the need for greater public awareness.

In conclusion, Georgian banks are active in financing renewable energy technologies for SMEs, with ProCredit Bank leading in project financing. However, the banks' reliance on international financial institution resources and challenges such as collateral requirements and insufficient financial education pose

obstacles to broader SME participation in renewable energy adoption.

The next target groups of the research include, on one hand, state agencies such as the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia—specifically the Department of Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Development—and the Georgian National Energy and Water Supply Regulatory Commission (GNERC). On the other hand, the research also targets representatives from professional associations such as the Georgian Renewable Energy Development Association (GREDA), the Energy Community of Georgia, and international organizations such as WEG (World Experience for Georgia) and the Elizabet Eristavi - Energy Training Center.

Participants were sent a questionnaire via email, which consisted of five questions. The ages of the participants ranged from 28 to 55 years.

Question on What Could Increase Participation in Energy-Efficient and Renewable Energy Projects by SMEs in Georgia

Diagram 1: Indicators for Increasing Participation in Energy-Efficient and Renewable Energy Projects by SMEs

Forty percent of respondents emphasized the need to raise awareness, particularly through more practical projects. Thirty percent identified the existence of additional enabling mechanisms, such as PPAs, feed-in tariffs, net metering, and origin certificates, as significant factors. Twenty percent mentioned the importance of reducing regulations and administrative barriers, as well as cutting subsidies on electricity. Finally, ten percent highlighted the need for proper regulation.

Question on What Main Enabling Measures Have Been Taken and What Is Planned to Promote Green Economy Development

Diagram 2: Current and Future Directions for Promoting Green Economy Development

Seventy-three percent of respondents mentioned the power auctions announced by the Ministry of Economy (CFD). Thirteen percent highlighted the role of GNERC and the importance of net metering systems, while fourteen percent discussed the need for further improvement of the Energy Ministry's support in this area.

Question on Recommendations for Increasing SME Participation in Energy-Efficient and Renewable Energy Projects

Diagram 3: Recommendations for Increasing SME Participation in Energy-Efficient and Renewable Energy Projects

Sixty-three percent of respondents advocate for increased awareness and more public projects. Twenty-five percent consider the establishment of appropriate regulatory and monitoring laws and agencies (such as energy efficiency laws, enforcement mechanisms for these laws, and support for ESCOs) as essential, while twelve percent suggest reducing electricity tariff subsidies.

Question on Measures Being Taken to Improve Access to Finance

Diagram 4: Measures to Improve Access to Finance

Fifty-two percent of respondents mentioned the 'Produce in Georgia' project, twenty-six percent referred to the Ministry of Economy's energy auctions (CFD), thirteen percent mentioned the EBRD's enabling program, and nine percent believe that no sufficient measures are currently being taken.

Question on What Is Being Done to Support the Development of SME Skills and the Promotion of Entrepreneurial Culture

Diagram 5: Measures to Support the Development of SME Skills and Entrepreneurial Culture

Seventy-two percent of respondents consider various types of seminars and training, primarily conducted by the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development, to be appropriate. Fourteen percent mentioned donor organization projects, while fourteen percent did not answer this question.

The study also targeted companies using solar power systems, aiming to assess the profitability of these installations. Three companies that have been utilizing solar technology for over a year participated (see Table 1: Installed Capacity and Financial Indicators).

Aqua Geo LLC (Sno): This company installed a 664.6 kW solar system, costing \$300,000, with support from Helios Energy Georgia and the "Produce in Georgia" program. The system, financed through a Bank of Georgia loan with a 10.9% interest rate (7% covered by the program), meets all the company's energy needs. The expected payback period is 3 years.

Golden Hands: A small enterprise that installed a 120.4 kW solar system, costing \$65,000, with assistance from the "Produce in Georgia" program. The loan interest rate was reduced from 11% to 4%. The system eliminated the company's monthly electricity expenditure of 3,000 GEL. The company actively uses net metering to credit surplus electricity to other locations.

DG Consulting: This small enterprise installed a 108 kW solar system, costing \$70,000, with funding from the "Agro Credit" program, allowing for a 2% loan interest rate. The expected payback period is 4 years. Besides financial savings, the system has prevented 121 tons of CO2 emissions within two years.

Table 1:

Installed Capacity and Financial Indicators

Station Name	Installed Capacity	Annual Generation	Total Investment	Payback Period
Golden Hands	102 kW	120,386 kWh	\$65,000	4 years
Aqua Geo	665.6 kW	861,300 kWh	\$300,000	4 years
DG Consulting	108 kW	140,400 kWh	\$70,000	4 years

Recommendations and Findings:

Awareness: A significant challenge is the lack of information on energy-efficient technologies within the SME sector. Disseminating information about successful projects could encourage similar initiatives.

Donor Co-financing: SMEs currently using solar power systems recommend green technology transitions with donor support. Without co-financing, extended payback periods could deter investment.

State Support: While international co-financing programs are effective, additional state programs are necessary to bolster sector growth.

Barriers: In-depth interviews revealed barriers for SMEs in implementing solar energy, such as low awareness of net metering and skepticism about renewable energy.

Solar System Types: SMEs use three types of solar power technologies: Autonomous (OFF-GRID),

Grid-Tied (GRID-TIED), and Hybrid-Microgrid (MICRO GRID). Companies import solar components mainly from China or Europe, offering warranties ranging from 25 to 30 years for capacity and 5 to 10 years for products.

Net Metering: Awareness of net metering is low, causing doubts and hindering renewable energy adoption. Net metering allows excess solar energy to be fed into the grid, offsetting household energy needs when solar production is low.

Financing: Focus group participants identified financing sources like the "Preferential Agrocredit" state program, which offers loans with a 5% interest rate above the National Bank of Georgia's rate for amounts between 1.5 to 3 million GEL.

Conclusions

SMEs often prioritize cost reduction and short-term profitability over long-term investments and environmentally friendly technologies. However, investing in energy-efficient and renewable energy technologies can offer significant benefits.

Limited funding from Georgian commercial banks is partly due to the high risk associated with SMEs and a low level of awareness about energy efficiency and solar technology projects among both banks and SMEs.

Georgian banks prefer to finance large companies, which often receive preferential loans for energy-efficient and renewable energy technologies. SMEs face high interest rates and stringent collateral requirements, which were not detailed by surveyed bank employees. This is confirmed by SSI research.

Banks use their resources and targeted credit lines from international financial institutions to finance renewable energy projects, potentially offering additional benefits to clients.

Georgian banks play a significant role in supporting SMEs in adopting renewable energy technologies. However, the lack of detailed information about loan approval processes and solutions to challenges faced by borrowers is a study limitation. Addressing these challenges could reveal more potential for sustainable development and economic growth.

Despite using international financial resources for financing, Georgian banks show dissatisfaction with their reliance on external funds and often refrain from using their resources after these projects are completed.

SMEs primarily rely on their resources for funding energy-efficient and renewable energy technologies, due to limited information on funding opportunities from state and international institutions.

Although the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development has announced capacity auctions to support renewable energy with the CFD mechanism (contract for difference model), there is little interest among SMEs. This scheme mainly supports large-scale projects, with limited interest in financing SMEs.

The Ministry of Energy has received a few requests for funding energy-efficient and solar energy projects. This lack of demand is due to insufficient

knowledge about the potential benefits and an overemphasis on perceived risks.

Low electricity consumption prices in Georgia limit the demand for energy-efficient and solar energy technologies, and thus the investment in these areas.

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